

Examining the motivating factors to join in police force among Women Police: An Empirical Study

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ABSTRACT

In this contemporary world, balancing the life and work is a serious issue to the working women. that too, working in police force is really a challenge to the women since it is traditionally a male dominated profession. Hence an attempt is made to examine the factors which are all influencing the women to choose police force as their career. Survey method is used to collect the data from the respondents through structured questionnaire from previous studies. Purposive sampling method is used to select the sample for data collection. As Tamilnadu has more number of Women Police when compared with other states in India, Tamilnadu is chosen as study area. Statistical Package for Social Science software is used to analyze the gathered data. Cronbach alpha value is used to check the internal consistency of the instrument which is used to collect the data for this study. This study found that "job security" , "power and authority" , "Profession carries prestige" and "Because of friends and relative already in police force" are the main forcing factors to choose police as the career. There is little difference among marital status wise categorised respondents and religious wise categorised respondents with regards to the motivational factors. Married and Hindu categorised respondents are saying that "Job security" is the most influential factor. Divorced and Christian categorised respondents are saying that "power and authority" is the very important motivational factor and Single and Muslim categorised respondents are saying that "Profession carries prestige" is the most influential factor to join in the police force.

1. Introduction

The employment of women police involves a variety of benefits, which have frequently been denied or underestimated. Equity in policing supports the global mission to create genuine equality and independence for women, including through employment and better delivery of social services (United Nations, 2009).Hence the women also has some important role in policing but, reality is , the number of women police in India is less when compared with their male counter parts even though women represents half of the human resource of India. To identify the reason behind this under representation of women in police force, the researcher took an attempt to identify the most influential factors which makes the currently working women police to join in this police force.

2. Background of the study

"Job security" and "respect/recognition" are the main factors to choose a police career and "Job security" & "Benefits offered by that job" are motivating the police women to continue in the service and then, "Unclear Career development policies" and "Work related practices" are affecting the performance of police women.(Sahgal, Indian, Relations, & Jan, 2007).

The 'women police movement' of the early-twentieth century was only successful in creating a very small space for female officers by making their role an extension of social welfare work. Women police were often unsworn, appointed on lower pay rates, without any rank structure and without a

pension scheme, and they were subject to dismissal if they married (Prenzler, 2002).

The entry and expansion of women police was, in general, fiercely opposed by police managers and police union leaders. On the job, women were often undermined by colleagues' lack of support, by sexual harassment, and by discrimination in deployment and promotion (Hunt, 1990; Brown and Heidensohn, 2000).

The incursion of women into traditionally 'male' occupations has been opposed, resisted, and undermined wherever it has occurred. In few other occupations, however, has their entry been more vigorously fought e on legal, organisational, informal, and interpersonal levels e than in policing (Martin, 1980: 79).

From the support of above reviews, the following objectives were framed,

1. To know the most influential factor to choose police career among women police.
2. To know the most motivating factor to choose police force as their career with regards to the demographic profile specifically.

To explore the above mentioned objective, the following hypothesis were framed,

1. There is a significant difference among marital status wise categorised respondents with regards to motivational factors to join in this police force

2. There is a significant difference among religious wise categorised respondents with regards to motivational factors to join in this police force

3. Research Methodology

The type of research used in this study is descriptive in nature. Purposive sampling method was used to choose the sample. The researcher has distributed 250 questionnaire but, the research has got only 226 valid responses after deleting non responses and outliers. The researcher has adopted the instrument which was used in Raganella and White (2004) study, a modified version of the survey developed by Lester

(1983). The instrument has 2 sections. The first section is dealt with the items related to demographic profile of the respondents and the second section is dealt with the items to find out which are all the motivational factors to women to choose the police field as their career options. SPSS Software was used to analyse the gathered data. Frequency analysis, Reliability analysis, Mean analysis, One Way ANOVA and split file option are applied in this study to analyse the data.

4. Data Analysis

Frequency Analysis of demographic of the respondents

Table1: Data Profile

Variable		Frequency	Percentage
Age	Less than 25 years	20	8.8
	25 years to 35 years	119	52.7
	35 years to 45 years	68	30.1
	More than 45 years	19	8.4
Educational Qualification	SSLC	23	10.2
	HSC	95	42.0
	Graduate	101	44.7
	Post Graduate	7	3.1
Marital Status	Married	135	59.7
	Single	71	31.4
	Divorced	14	6.2
	Widow	6	2.7
Religion	Hindu	173	76.5
	Christian	47	20.8
	Muslim	6	2.7

Source: Primary Data

The above table shows that most of the respondents (52.7%) are in the age category "25 years to 35 years". 44.7 percentage of the respondents have completed graduation.

Most of the respondents(59.7%) are married and 76.5 percentage of the respondents are from Hindu religion.

Reliability Analysis

Table 2: Reliability Statistics

Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
.902	17

The above table indicates that reliability of the instrument which is used in this study is good enough.

Mean Analysis:

1. Motivational factors for whole sample

Table 3: Motivational factors for whole sample

Motivational Factors	Mean	Rank	Std. Deviation	Skewness	Kurtosis
Job security	2.25	I	0.777	-0.473	-1.197
Power and authority	2.24	II	0.828	-0.477	-1.379
Profession carries prestige	2.19	III	0.799	-0.35	-1.35
Excitement of work	2.1	IV	0.796	-0.177	-1.4
Opportunity to help people in the community	2.08	V	0.774	-0.132	-1.318

To fight crime	2.08	V	0.761	-0.133	-1.262
because of friends or relatives who were police officers	2.07	VII	0.871	-0.127	-1.673
Life long dream	1.95	VIII	0.789	0.082	-1.386
Suitable job to the ability	1.95	VIII	0.725	0.075	-1.092
Good companionship with co workers	1.94	X	0.793	0.107	-1.4
lack of career alternatives	1.92	XI	0.848	0.146	-1.596
salary	1.89	XII	0.83	0.2	-1.522
To enforce the laws of society	1.88	XIII	0.788	0.21	-1.361
use this job as a stepping stone to a better career	1.86	XIV	0.748	0.241	-1.18
Job benefits (medical allowance)	1.82	XV	0.773	0.332	-1.258
Opportunities for career advancement	1.79	XVI	0.84	0.411	-1.462
structured like the military	1.7	XVII	0.831	0.613	-1.28

Source: Primary data

The above table reveals that what are all the most important factors or reasons to why women choose police force as their career options. Most of the respondents accepting that "Job security" ($\mu=2.25$ and $\sigma =0.77$) is the most

influential factor. "Power and Authority" ($\mu=2.24$ and $\sigma =.828$) is the second most influential factor. Skewness and kurtosis values are in between the limit -2 to +2 which indicates that the data collected here is normally distributed.

2. Motivational factors among Married, Single, Divorced and Widow

Table 4: Motivational factors among Married, Single, Divorced and Widow-Mean rank & ANOVA

Motivational factors	Married (N=135)		Single (N=71)		Divorced (N=14)		Widow (N=6)		F	Sig
	Mean	Rank	Mean	Rank	Mean	Rank	Mean	Rank		
Job security	2.27	1	2.20	2	2.57	2	2.17	3	.956	.414
Job benefits (medical allowance)	1.87	13	1.85	13	1.93	11	1.33	8	.986	.400
Opportunities for career advancement	1.79	14	1.89	11	1.79	13	1.33	8	.866	.460
Opportunity to help people in the community	2.15	4	2.04	6	2.14	9	1.83	5	.564	.640
Excitement of work	2.10	6	2.08	4	2.42	4	1.67	6	1.454	.228
To fight crime	2.17	3	2.06	5	2.57	2	1.67	6	2.732	.045
Good companionship with co workers	1.97	9	1.90	10	2.43	3	1.50	7	2.518	.054
To enforce the laws of society	1.92	10	1.85	13	2.14	9	1.50	7	1.076	.360
Profession carries prestige	2.13	5	2.34	1	2.21	7	1.67	6	1.908	.129
life long dream	2.01	7	1.79	15	2.29	5	1.17	10	4.435	.005
Suitable job to the ability	2.01	7	1.87	12	2.28	6	1.33	8	3.204	.024
Use this job as a stepping stone to a better career	1.91	11	1.80	14	2.14	9	1.00	11	3.662	.013
salary	1.90	12	1.96	9	2.07	10	1.67	6	.390	.760
because of friends or relatives who were police officers	1.99	8	2.01	7	2.19	8	2.33	1	.550	.649
structured like the military	1.66	16	1.69	16	1.92	12	1.00	11	1.831	.142
lack of career alternatives	1.78	15	1.97	8	1.93	11	2.32	2	1.547	.203
Power and authority	2.26	2	2.11	3	2.64	1	2.00	4	1.894	.131

Source: Primary Data

The above table reveals that married respondents have given first rank to "Job security", respondents categorised as single have given first rank to "Profession carries prestige", respondents who are all categorised as Divorced says that "power and authority" is the main motivational factor where as Widow categorised respondents have given first rank to

"because of friends and relatives in police force". Totally five mean differences achieved statistical significance. Thus, there is some changes among the married, Single, divorced and widow categorised respondents with regards to these five items at 5 percentage significant level.

3. Motivational factors among Hindu, Christian and Muslim Respondents

Table 5: Motivational factors among Hindu, Christian and Muslim Respondents-Mean Ranks & ANOVA

Motivational factors	Hindu (N=173)		Christian(N=47)		Muslim (N=6)		F	Sig
	Mean	Rank	Mean	Rank	Mean	Rank		
Job security	2.26	1	2.28	2	2.32	4	.032	.969
Job benefits (medical allowance)	1.87	14	1.79	12	1.81	9	.228	.797
Opportunities for career advancement	1.80	15	1.87	11	1.67	11	.234	.792
Opportunity to help people in the community	2.08	6	2.15	4	2.50	2	.964	.383
Excitement of work	2.13	4	2.02	8	2.17	5	.356	.701
To fight crime	2.11	5	2.26	3	2.33	3	.875	.418
Good companionship with co workers	1.94	9	2.09	6	1.83	7	.742	.477
To enforce the laws of society	1.91	12	1.79	12	2.50	2	2.205	.113
Profession carries prestige	2.15	3	2.28	2	2.67	1	1.552	.214
lifelong dream	1.95	8	1.91	9	1.81	9	.089	.915
Suitable job to the ability	1.94	9	2.06	7	2.00	6	.539	.584
Use this job as a stepping stone to a better career	1.90	13	1.74	13	1.80	10	.793	.454
salary	1.92	11	1.89	10	2.33	3	.740	.478
because of friends or relatives who were police officers	1.99	7	2.13	5	1.83	7	.559	.573
structured like the military	1.69	16	1.62	14	1.50	12	.264	.768
lack of career alternatives	1.93	10	1.62	14	1.83	7	2.651	.073
Power and authority	2.19	2	2.38	1	2.33	3	1.038	.356

Source: Primary data

According to the numerical values given in the above table, Hindu religious respondents are saying that "Job security" is the most influential factor to join in police force. Christian categorised respondents are saying that "power and authority" is the most motivational factor where as Muslim categorised respondents are saying that "profession carries prestige" is the important inducing factor to join in the police force. Here, only two mean differences achieve statistical significance. Thus, religious categorised respondents are differing with regards to these 2 items at 10 percent significant level.

5. Conclusion and Discussions

This study found that "job security", "power and authority", "Profession carries prestige" and "Because of friends and relative already in police force" are the main forcing factors to choose police as the career. There is little difference among marital status wise categorised respondents and religious wise categorised respondents with regards to the motivational

factors. Married and Hindu categorised respondents are saying that "Job security" is the most influential factor. Divorced and Christian categorised respondents are saying that "power and authority" is the very important motivational factor and Single and Muslim categorised respondents are saying that "Profession carries prestige" is the most influential factor to join in the police force.

From this study, Police administration is suggested to focus on the strength of women police which is already low when compared with their male counter parts, by making some changes in policies such as arranging crèche facility, Rest room facility, adequate leave and allotting desk duties in the time of pregnancy and menopause and equal preference to women in career advancement and deploying authority and responsibilities. By seeing these job benefits women might be motivated strongly to join in police force as well as to retain in that job till their retirement stage.

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